

Optimized Weld Design of Gusset Plates to increase the Fatigue Resistance of Hollow Sections Joints

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Keywords

Fatigue Resistance; Hollow Section Joints; Longitudinal Stiffener; High Strength Steel; weld optimization; notch stress concept.

Abstract

As investigated in the preceding project FOSTA P1442 the fatigue behaviour of welded tubular joints can be increased remarkably by using shape-optimized gusset plates. It also was shown that the weld seam geometry, the weld preparation and the weld execution have a significant impact on fatigue strength for which there is no design or manufacturing recommendation. This is even more important when using High Strength Steels. In the new research project FOSTA P1735 this optimization is addressed. In a first step, basic research on five different weld shapes is carried out for steel grades S355 and S700. This investigation is based on parametric studies by FEM and fatigue tests for verification and will build the basis for the implementation of these types of optimized weld-shape to gusset plates in K- and X-joints subjected to fatigue stress. In this paper the findings of these preliminary basic tests and FEM studies are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The research project FOSTA P1442 [1] demonstrated that geometrically optimized gusset plates significantly enhance the fatigue resistance of hollow section K-joints compared to conventional welded designs.

While weldments with run-off beads proved effective in [1], existing data on run-in/run-off bead optimization remains limited – primarily from crane-specific studies (e.g., FOSTA P293 [2], FOSTA P512 [3]). Consequently, these details lack a robust statistical foundation for assigning fatigue detail categories in current standards.

To address this gap, the follow-up project FOSTA P1735 was initiated by the Centre of Competence for Tubes and Hollow Sections (KoRoH - CCTH) in Karlsruhe and the University of Applied Sciences in Munich (HM Munich). As part of this work, a systematic numerical study is being conducted to evaluate key geometric parameters, including weld bead characteristics (cross-section, length, flank angle, and toe radius) and base-plate dimensions (stiffener thickness, height, length, and plate width/length).

This paper presents the findings of these investigations, which serve as the foundation for the project's next phase: transferring the optimal fatigue-resistant design (identified through the basic tests on plate specimens) to 16 X-joint

and 10 K-joint specimens with gusset plates. The target geometry features a brace-to-chord width ratio β of 0.8 and uses high-strength steel (S700).

2 NUMERICAL MODEL

Taking advantage of the small test specimens' axisymmetry, the numerical modelling was performed using an eighth-model approach that uses the symmetry across all three spatial planes. The analysis utilized the CalculiX finite element solver paired with ParaView for post-processing.

In the critical weld transition zone where the tapered weld meets the keyhole notch between stiffener and base plate, the model incorporated a defined notch radius of 1 mm. This area received a fine discretization with an element edge length of 0.25 mm to capture stress concentrations. The mesh gradually coarsened to element sizes of 1.5 mm specified for the YZ and XY symmetry planes and 5 mm elements along the free edges. All radius regions maintained a consistent 30° inclination for element normals.

Figure 1 illustrates this discretization scheme, which employed 8-node tetrahedral elements with reduced integration. While these modelling choices don't permit exact quantification of absolute notch stresses according to DVS 0905 [4], the consistent discretization applied across

all design variants ensures valid comparative results between configurations.

This modelling approach, combined with analysis of the resulting notch stress factors K_t , enabled a systematic investigation of various weld parameters. The study examined multiple geometric variations including weld profile shapes, flank angles, and length parameters to determine their influence on fatigue performance.

Figure 1: Example for the discretization for the basic investigations

3 PARAMETRIC STUDY

3.1 Basic weld layout

Together with the involved industrial partners, e.g. from crane construction and agricultural machinery construction, five different variants were selected to be examined in more detail (cp. Table 1). For all variants it was agreed to use outgoing fillet welds (FW) to the end of the gusset plates (Figure 2).

Table 1: investigated variants

Variant	Description
I	FW at the gusset end
II	Circumferential around the gusset plates
III	FW at the gusset end, straight outgoing without tack weld
IV	FW at the gusset end, outgoing dovetail weld without tack weld
V	FW at the gusset end, outgoing dovetail weld with tack weld

Figure 2: Variants to be examined

3.2 Numerical Findings

For all variants, parametric studies have been carried out. Different lengths of the straight outgoing welds with and without root notches and different angles of the dovetail welds with and without root notches were examined alongside other variants.

Variant III was modelled with and without root notches and with different lengths of the straight outgoing welds. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show some examples of the FE studies carried out.

Figure 3: Variant II resulting in $K_{t,WE} = 3.20$ at the end of the weld.

Figure 4: Variant III with and without modelling of a root notch. Outgoing length of the weld $l = 25$ mm

Comparing the results of both models, it becomes clear that resulting stress concentration factors at the ends of the welds $K_{t,WE} = 2.80$ and $K_{t,WE} = 2.70$ are 12.5 % and 15.6 % lower compared to Var. II with the circumferential weld at the end of the plate. On the other hand, at the transition of the gusset plate to the weld the notch stress factor results to $K_{t,LS} = 3.86$ for the model without modeling a root failure. Even higher values result with a keyhole representing a root notch of $K_{t,LS} = 4.20$ resp. $K_{t,WK} = 6.77$ at the weld root.

In a similar way, the dovetail weld ends have been investigated. In addition to the length of the outgoing welds also the angle of the dovetails was varied. The notch numbers were determined at the same positions as for the straight outgoing welds (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Variant IV with modelling of a root notch and with the length of the weld $l = 25$ mm

Figure 6 shows a graph with the development of the notch efficiency factors as function of the total weld length, which depends on the investigated angles.

Figure 10: Combined evaluation of all variants of series A

5 SUMMARY

Based on numerical studies, five fatigue test series with optimized weld geometries were designed and experimentally evaluated. The results of Series A-I (welds ending at the plate edges) and Series A-II (circumferential welds at the plate ends) align well with the fatigue class Detail Category 63 specified in [6] for comparable notch details.

In contrast, Series A-IV and A-V demonstrated approximately 50% higher fatigue resistance, highlighting the significant benefits of weld shape optimization. It should be noted that all tests were conducted using high-strength steel with a yield strength of 700 MPa.

6 OUTLOOK

The experimental program will be extended to investigate Variants III, IV, and V, focusing on the effects of steel grade and plate thickness on fatigue performance.

In parallel, numerical studies will be expanded to achieve the project's ultimate objective: transferring these findings to welded hollow sections to optimize their fatigue resistance (see Figure 10). This dual approach aims to bridge experimental insights with practical applications for lightweight structural design.

Figure 10. Common evaluation of all variants of series A

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Herion, A. Dürr, P. Ladendorf, and M. Winkler, "Final report: Increase of fatigue strength of hollow section joints made of high strength steels by shape-optimized gusset plates, FOSTA P1442/32/2019 / S 0024/10258/19". 2023.
- [2] F. Mang, S. Herion, G. Sedlacek, C. Müller, M. Kästner, „Bemessungsregeln zur Beurteilung des Ermüdungsverhaltens von Kranstrukturen – Klassifizierung von kranbauspezifischen Kerbdetails, Forschung für die Praxis P 293“, Studiengesellschaft Stahlanwendung e.V., Düsseldorf, 2000.
- [3] R. Puthli, S. Herion, J. Bergers, G. Sedlacek, C. Müller, J. Stötzel, S. Höhler, Ö. Bucak, „Beurteilung des Ermüdungsverhaltens von Kranstrukturen bei Einsatz hoch- und ultrahochfester Stähle: Forschungsvorhaben P 512“
- [4] Merkblatt DVS 0905:2021-05 Industrielle Anwendung des Kerbspannungskonzeptes für den Ermüdungsfestigkeitsnachweis von Schweißverbindungen, DVS Media GmbH, Düsseldorf, 2021.
- [5] DIN EN 1990:2021-10, Eurocode: Basis of structural design; German version EN 1990:2002 + A1:2005 + A1:2005/AC:2010, <https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/3291403>
- [6] DIN EN 1993-1-9:2010-12, Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-9: Fatigue; German version EN 1993-1-9:2005 + AC:2009, <https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/1722660>
- [7] S. Herion, A. Dürr, P. Ladendorf, and M. Winkler, "Final report: Optimized weld seam design of tubular connections through gusset plates for an increase in fatigue strength", FOSTA P 1735/25/2023 / S 0024/10281/23'. expected 2026.